

Inputs to the ATLANTIC OCEAN RESEARCH ALLIANCE Marine Microbiome Roadmap

ENVIRONMENT AND CLIMATE

Vision Statement
The marine microbiome will be at the heart of understanding ocean ecosystems and the sustainability of the services they provide to society

Background
Just as the human microbiome is central to our health, the ocean microbiome is key to a healthy and resilient biosphere.

Microbes permeate the ocean and their activities deeply influence its chemistry, physics, and underpin all marine life. The marine microbiome is sensitive to environmental stress and shapes ecosystems across the entire planet. Vitality, this also affects our planet's climate system, as marine microbes are responsible for pumping atmospheric carbon into the oceans and preventing the release of methane from the ocean's depths into the atmosphere. They are also key to sustaining the ecosystem services that humans rely on and thus highly relevant to multiple aspects of the Sustainable Development Agenda. For example, their diverse metabolic abilities can deactivate and recycle waste products and pollutants while provisioning food webs and fisheries with essential nutrients. Simultaneously, some kinds of marine microbes pose significant threats to living systems through their ability to cause disease, produce toxins, resist antibiotics, and form harmful algal blooms and oxygen-depleted dead zones. These roles also make microbiomes sensitive and broad indicators of the state, functions, changes, and health of marine ecosystems.

Despite the importance of the marine microbiome to both science and society, our ability to observe it at scale is underdeveloped and under-coordinated compared to current physio-chemical ocean observation efforts. However, recent advances and the falling costs of technologies such as high-throughput sequencing, e.g. of eDNA, remote sensing and autonomous sampling, and emerging coordination networks are a game changer.

We are now capable of mainstreaming microbiome observations in ocean science and operations at large, complementing existing capacities with new biological and ecological perspectives. Integrating microbiomes within ecosystem models will help to improve our ability to better predict and respond to climate variation

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About this document

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Summary for publication

The **Marine Microbiome Roadmap** was published by the AORAC-SA project in February 2020.

The Roadmap is the result of an international cooperative effort between Canada, the European Union and the United States of America produced within the AORA framework and consistent with the Galway Statement on Atlantic Ocean Cooperation. The roadmap has been put together with inputs of Principal Investigators of numerous other projects. Among these, Blue-Action has contributed to one specific section of the Roadmap, the one on “Environment and Climate”.

Work carried out

The project AORAC-SA

In the Blue-Action work plan, a specific deliverable was added to the list of the WP6 Clustering for Blue Growth activities to link to the project H2020 AORAC-SA and provide inputs to this project.

The AORAC-SA project is a H2020-funded coordination and support action, funded by the European Commission under the call [BG-14-2014 - Supporting international cooperation initiatives: Atlantic Ocean Cooperation Research Alliance](#).

Abstract of the AORAC-SA project

The Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Coordination and Support Action (AORAC-SA) is designed to provide scientific, technical and logistical support to the European Commission in developing and implementing trans-Atlantic Marine Research Cooperation between the European Union, the United States of America and Canada. The Coordination and Support Action (CSA) is carried out within the framework of the Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance as outlined in the Galway Statement on Atlantic Ocean Cooperation (May 2013). Recognising the evolving nature of the Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance, the hallmark of this proposal is that it is flexible, responsive, inclusive, efficient, innovative, value-adding and supportive.

To support the Commission in negotiations with the USA and Canada on trans-Atlantic Ocean Research Cooperation, the AORAC-SA support and governance structure comprises a Secretariat and Management Team, guided by a high-level Operational Board, representative of the major European Marine Research Programming and Funding Organisations as well as those of the USA and Canada. This structure is further able to draw on significant marine research expertise and experience through its partner organisations

The CSA, reporting to the Commission representatives of the Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance, will be responsible for the organisation of expert and stakeholder meetings, workshops and conferences required by the Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance and related to identified research priorities (e.g. marine ecosystem-approach, observing systems, marine biotechnology, aquaculture, ocean literacy, seabed and benthic habitat mapping), support actions (e.g. shared access to infrastructure, dissemination and knowledge transfer, establishment of a knowledge sharing platform) and other initiatives as they arise, taking into account related Horizon 2020 supported trans-Atlantic projects (e.g. BG1, BG8 and BG13) and on-going national and EU collaborative projects (e.g. FP7).

Genesis of the Blue-Action contribution AORAC-SA and its Roadmap

Being AORAC-SA one of the main projects focusing on Blue Growth, our idea was to create a placeholder for a deliverable to bring the two projects together to exchange knowledge on topics to be identified at a later stage, during the implementation of both projects, allowing us both maximum flexibility in picking up the specific topic to collaborate upon.

One of the foci of AORAC-SA is "food from the ocean", and this is linked to the [UN SDG 14](#). "Oceans serve as the world's largest source of protein, with more than 3 billion people relying on them oceans as their primary source. As billions of people depend on oceans for their livelihood and food source and on the transboundary nature of oceans, increased efforts and interventions are needed to conserve and sustainably use ocean resources at all levels. One of the foci of Blue-Action is also the development of climate services for marine fisheries and fish predictions in the Atlantic (CS4¹).

Climate change is causing warming sea temperatures and increasing ocean acidification, fundamentally altering marine ecosystems. In particular, fish species are responding by changing their distributions productivity and the timing of their migrations, with consequences for conservation, fisheries and tourism.

We exchanged with AORAC-SA how we could bring expertise of the Blue-Action community to AORAC-CSA around this topic. Later on, following a specific request of AORAC-SA, Blue-Action contributed to the design workshop of the Roadmap, with specific inputs to breakout session on Environment and climate, on "*How climate changes in Arctic can affect the North Atlantic marine microbiome*" at the first workshop held in Reykjavik on 21-24 October 2019. The workshop was organized with the scope to provide a framework for a roadmap for Marine Microbiome Observations in the Atlantic.

Topics for discussion were the following:

- How to map the Atlantic microbiome?
- How to use omics-based microbiome information for informing the description of the food webs?
- Indicators of Good Environmental Status: how to include -omics?
- An interconnected Ocean: how to consider space and time into one single framework? What is the role of oceanic transport?
- How to establish a strong link with modelling development?
- How to guarantee efficient data standardization, storage and dissemination?
- How to link with EU infrastructures, MBON, GOOS etc?

Key contributions from Blue-Action involved participation in all sessions and co-leading and presenting breakout sessions in the Environment and Climate section.

As a follow up of the workshop, Blue-Action co-authored the Environment and Climate section of the final roadmap which was published in February 2020.

Why the roadmap?

New insights on the significance of the microscopic scale of ocean life have shown this level affects almost every aspect of our lives (health, food, industry, ecosystems). For society's future, we need to investigate the science of marine microbiomes, integrate the novel technologies discovered and initiate policies that foster truly sustainable marine development. To ensure early coordination and interoperability guided by a shared vision, it is necessary to bring together science, industry and policy makers to advance the "Next Great Exploration of the Oceans".

The Pillars of the Roadmap

Within the marine microbiome Roadmap, three thematic pillars have been identified by scientists and policy makers, all supported with underlying cross-cutting elements:

- Environment and Climate,
- Food Value Chain and
- Biodiscovery.

Blue-Action key contributions to the Roadmap

The Havstovan team of Blue-Action worked on the specific chapter on Environment and Climate (page 9-11) in the Roadmap stressing the importance of establishing the bidirectional links between the Atlantic Microbiome and environment and climate.

The Atlantic Microbiome influences climate through sequestration of atmospheric Carbon dioxide and production of climatically active compounds. Conversely a key contribution is the recognition that climatic changes in environmental factors will influence the biogeography and provision of marine ecosystem services by the marine microbiome.

A key contribution was therefore to understand the links between microbiome observations and climatic hotspots by identifying the need to use IPCC prediction models to map appropriate spatial and temporal components of observational frameworks for Atlantic Microbiomes.

A second contribution was to highlight the need to identify the technological requirements and hurdles for successful implementation of monitoring programs that link climate observations with the provision of marine ecosystem services mediated by the microbiome.

Impacts

The work with AORAC-SA has contributed to the following expected impacts of Blue-Action:

Improve stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change

Improving innovation capacity and the integration of new knowledge

New insights on the significance of the microscopic scale of ocean life have shown this level affects almost every aspect of our lives (health, food, industry, ecosystems). For society's future, we need to investigate the science of marine microbiomes, integrate the novel technologies discovered and initiate

policies that foster truly sustainable marine development. To ensure early coordination and interoperability guided by a shared vision, it is necessary to bring together science, industry and policy makers to advance the “Next Great Exploration of the Oceans”.

Lessons learned

Across the Atlantic, there is a strong need to improve the bridge between environment observations, controlled experiments data science, and predictive modelling to create deep and validated understanding: monitoring programs need to link climate observations with the provision of marine ecosystem services mediated by the microbiome.

Contribution to the top level objectives of Blue-Action

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of all the objectives and specific goals indicated in the Description of the Action, part B, Section 1.1: <http://blue-action.eu/index.php?id=4019>

- **Objective 7 Fostering the capacity of key stakeholders to adapt and respond to climate change and boosting their economic growth**
- **Objective 8 Transferring knowledge to a wide range of interested key stakeholders**

Dissemination and exploitation of Blue-Action results

Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination activity	Name of the scientist (institution), title of the presentation, event	Place and date of the event	Type of Audience	Estimated number of persons reached	Link to Zenodo
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	Marine Microbiome Roadmap	//	General Public, Policy makers, Medias, Scientific Community (higher education, Research), Industry, Civil Society	113 views and 175 downloads (10 March 2020)	https://www.zenodo.org/record/3632526
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	Ian Salter (HAV), Workshop for the shaping of the Marine Microbiome Roadmap	21-24 October 2019, Reykjavik (IS)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	40	//
Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	Hjálmar Hátún (HAV), AORA working group on marine microbiome	5 February 2020, Brussels (BE)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	15	//

Peer reviewed articles

Title	Authors	Publication	DOI
Climate based multi-year predictions of the Barents Sea cod stock	M. Áρθun, B. Bogstad, U. Dawel, N. S. Keenlyside, A. B. Sandø, C. Schrum, G. Ottersen	PloS one, 13(10), e0206319.	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0206319
The subpolar gyre regulates silicate concentrations in the North Atlantic	H. Hátún, K. Azetsu-Scott, R. Somavilla, F. Rey, C. Johnson, M. Mathis, U. Mikolajewicz, P. Coupel, J.-É. Tremblay, S. Hartman, S. V. Pacariz, I. Salter & J. Ólafsson	Scientific Reports, 7: 14576	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-14837-4
Decreased influx of Calanus spp. into the south-western Norwegian Sea since 2003	Kristiansen, I., Hátún, H., Petursdottir, H., Gislason, A., Broms, C., Melle, W., Jacobsen, J. A., Eliassen, S. K., and Gaard, E.	Deep Sea Research	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2019.05.008
Environmentally Driven Ecological Fluctuations on the Faroe Shelf Revealed by Fish Juvenile Surveys	S. Jacobsen, E. Gaard, H. Hátún, P. Steingrund, K. M. H. Larsen, J. Reinert, S. R. Ólafsdóttir, M. Poulsen, H. B. M. Vang	Frontiers	In review
Traversing major nutrient fronts in the northeastern Atlantic – from the subpolar gyre to adjacent shelves	Hjálmar Hátún, Karin Margretha H. Larsen, Sólvá Káradóttir Eliassen, Mathis Moritz	Chemical Oceanography of Frontal Zones, Springer	In review

Uptake by the targeted audiences

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is *for the* general public (PU) is and is made available to the world via CORDIS.